

THE IMPORTANCE OF BEE EGGS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BEE FAMILY

¹N.A. Azizova, ²Sh.B. Bakaeva, ³Gulshoda Tolqinjanova Ulugbek qizi, ⁴Feruza Islomova
Mirzohidovna

¹Teacher of Department of Zoology and General Biology of BukhSU

²Teacher of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

^{3,4} Students of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *In the conditions of Bukhara, raising a family of bees is carried out seasonally. In early spring, up to 1000 eggs are laid by queen bees in a strong colony. Spawning varies seasonally. In the conditions of Bukhara, the egg-laying period of queen bees begins at the beginning of February. April and May are the most spawning season. In the spring, the bees have to provide additional food to the colony in order to lay good eggs. The result of supplementary feeding shows that, by increasing the productivity of worker bees, quality queen bee breeding technologies also lead to an increase in the number and weight of eggs and lead to the maturation of bee eggs at a high quality level. This determines the importance of bee eggs in the development of the bee family. It is important that the more and better the bee eggs are, the more the family is hardworking Spring, summer, winter and autumn seasonal feeding in beekeeping is very different. It is important to artificially feed the bee colony and raise the queen bee, which also leads to an increase in the number and weight of eggs. The weight of the bee eggs affects the quality of the queen bee, that is, the laying of a large number of eggs, the strength of the bee colony, the weight of the queen bee is much heavier, and the number of egg tubes in her ovary is somewhat higher.*

Keywords: *quality queen, flower pollen, egg tubes, wheatgrass water, control group, experimental group, queen bee, queen bee rearing from bee eggs, rearing bee family, queen rearing from bee larva, plastic cup, wing length, wing span, 3rd test , 3rd sternite*

With the onset of spring, the bee family's need for protein-rich foods is felt. It is very important to feed them with honey and sugar syrup during the period when there is little pollen and nectar in nature. In particular, feeding the bee colonies with the water of healthful wheat (sumalak), which is rich in vitamins, has a positive effect on the development of the bee colony. It makes them healthy. The daily egg-laying of queen bees increases and the provision of bee breeding in the hive is improved.

When raising a bee colony, the main focus is on making the bee colony strong. The strength of a bee colony depends on the quality of the only Queen bee in the colony. The quality of a queen bee is characterized by how many fertilized eggs she lays. Only the queen bee laying a large number of eggs in the family will ensure a strong bee colony, because such a queen bee weighs much more and has a slightly larger number of egg tubes in her ovary.

Many factors influence the weight of queen bees. Many factors can be the cause of these factors, such as the weight of bee eggs, the quality of the family of bees that raise bees in the production of queen bees, the supply of quality food, the arrival of natural flowers and pollen from the field, the surrounding environment, and the weather temperature.

Taking this into account, in accordance with the experiment carried out at

"Saidov Samad Sanoyevich dehqon fermer xo'jaligi " of Vobkent District, Bukhara Region, in artificial bee breeding, the weight of bee eggs and the quality indicators of bees, i.e. the daily weight of the bee and the number of egg tubes in her ovaries we studied the effect.

We took the weight of queen bee eggs with a special scoop made of goose down from the cells of the beehive frames, with a smooth tip, and measured it on their accurate electronic scale. We measured the weight of one-day queen bees on the same electronic scales. Before measurement, unfertilized queen bees were anesthetized with ether. To determine the number of oviducts of anesthetized queen bees, they were placed in 70% ethyl alcohol and removed for later examination.

Experiments were conducted in two variants. The queen bees raised in the I-experiment group were not fed additionally, and the rearing bee families in the II-experiment group were additionally given 10 liters of 50% sugar juice and one liter of grass wheat (sumalak) water. 200-250 mg once every two days was fed through the upper mangers of the rearing bee family. Information on the influence of bee egg size on the quality indicators of queen bees is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1

The influence of bee egg size on the quality of queen bees

Groups	n	Bee eggs weight	Weight of queen bees, mg	Number of egg tubes
The control is migrant queen bees	15	0.118±0.006	198.5±1.50	186.6±1.64
Experimental group 1st was not fed	105	0.109±0.005	196.4±1.66	170.8±1.59
Experiment 2nd fed	98	0.149±0.004	217.6±1.71	191.2±2.21

Table 1 shows that the average weight of 105 bee eggs in experimental group I was 0.109 mg. Grow from these eggs The weight of one-day-old queen bees was 196.4 mg, and the number of egg tubes in their ovaries was 170.8.

In experiment group II, when these families were fed with protein-rich grass wheat (sumalak) water, the picture was completely different, the average weight of 98 bee eggs was 0.149 mg., which is experiment I. was 0.4 40 mg more or 136.6% more than the group. It was 31.0 mg more than the control group.

Similarly, the weight of one-day unfertilized queen bees was 217.6 mg in experimental group II, or it was 21.2 mg higher than in experimental group I. This is an increase of 110.8%. it was 19.1 mg more than control group. Also, the number of egg tubes in the ovaries of queen bees was 191.2 units in experimental group II, which was 19.4 units more than in experimental group I, or it was 111.9% more. . Compared to the control group, it was 4.6 more.

It should be said that the weight of bee eggs played a big role in the formation of queen bees here for the life of bees. During the period of vital development of queen bees, they receive a large amount of food only from the milk of nurse bees in the family, therefore, even during the period of maturity of queen bees, a lot of milk residues remain unused in their hut (mother). Therefore, during the period of formation of the mother bees, they are provided with a sufficient amount of food.

Therefore, feeding the queen bees with additional protein foods has a great effect on their formation and development. Here, of course, they are fed additionally, and the temperature and humidity of the nest are taken into account when food comes from the field.

Conclusion. In addition to the formation and development of the queen bee, the addition of grass wheat water containing protein and vitamin nutrients (10×1 ratio) in addition to the content of her food, ensured the rapid development of the queen bee larvae. . Also, heavy weight bee eggs produced mature and healthy heavy weight queen bees with increased viability and disease resistance, and they were able to lay large numbers of eggs.

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